

QUBO Formulation of Entropy Maximization

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Abstract

In this brief note, the authors present an approach to formulating the maximization of entropy (Shannon) as an approximate QUBO problem.

Consider a simple triune p.m.f. : $\{1 - b - c, b, c\}$. For this p.m.f.,

$$H(X) = -(1 - b - c) \log(1 - b - c) - b \log(b) - c \log(c). \quad (1)$$

We next allow three binary decimal digits of precision for each of b and c . This yields a maximization in 6 variables, each of which can take values in $\{0, 1\}$. We make use of the following approximations:

$$\log(b) \approx \frac{b - 1}{0.693147} - \frac{(b - 1)^2}{1.3863}. \quad (2)$$

A similar approximation works for the logarithm of c and of $(1 - b - c)$. In terms of the three binary decimal digits of precision we can write $H(X)$ as

$$-(1 - 2^{-1}b_0 - 2^{-2}b_1 - 2^{-3}b_2 - 2^{-1}c_0 - 2^{-2}c_1 - 2^{-3}c_2) \log(1 - 2^{-1}b_0 - 2^{-2}b_1 - 2^{-3}b_2 - 2^{-1}c_0 - 2^{-2}c_1 - 2^{-3}c_2) \quad (3)$$

$$-(2^{-1}b_0 + 2^{-2}b_1 + 2^{-3}b_2) \log(2^{-1}b_0 + 2^{-2}b_1 + 2^{-3}b_2) \quad (4)$$

$$-(2^{-1}c_0 + 2^{-2}c_1 + 2^{-3}c_2) \log(2^{-1}c_0 + 2^{-2}c_1 + 2^{-3}c_2). \quad (5)$$

In the same vein, we can expand b^2 as

$$2^{-6}b_2 + 2^{-3}b_2b_0 + 2^{-4}b_2b_1 + 2^{-2}b_0 + 2^{-4}b_1 + 2^{-2}b_0b_1. \quad (6)$$

However, when we come to b^3 and other cubic terms, we will encounter triune terms like $b_0b_1b_2$ in the expansion. Each such term can be replaced by a new variable. For example, we can replace $b_0b_1b_2$ by y and add the constraints: $y \leq b_0$, $y \leq b_1$, $y \leq b_2$ and $y \geq b_0 + b_1 + b_2 - 2$ to ensure equivalence while complying with the QUBO format requirements¹. In future work, we will extend this methodology to capacity calculation. The results will then be compared with the Blahut-Arimoto approach results.

¹Credit goes to an AI model for suggesting this.